

THE IMPACT OF INTRINSIC OR EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION ON TEENAGERS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

Abdulkhæva Nodirabegim

Teacher of Nordic International University

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Abstract. *The article provides information on how intrinsic or extrinsic motivation affects students' English language learning in connection with the Critical Period Hypothesis. Students learn English better when they are intrinsically motivated, or extrinsically motivated, that is, some students learn English because of their interest in the language. This is considered intrinsic motivation, while other students are forced to learn English because of their parents' wishes because they want to work in a better job, and to name but a few.*

Keywords: *intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, the Critical Period Hypothesis, teenagers, dominance, communication, acquire.*

Аннотация. *В статье представлена информация о том, как внутренняя или внешняя мотивация влияет на изучение английского языка студентами в связи с гипотезой критического периода. Студенты изучают английский лучше, когда они имеют внутреннюю или внешнюю мотивацию, то есть некоторые студенты изучают английский язык из-за своего интереса к языку. Это считается внутренней мотивацией, в то время как другие студенты вынуждены изучать английский язык по желанию своих родителей, потому что они хотят работать на лучшей работе, и это лишь некоторые из них.*

Ключевые слова: *внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация, гипотеза критического периода, подростки, доминирование, общение, приобретение.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada kritik davr gipotezasi bilan bog'liq holda o'quvchilarning ingliz tilini o'rganishiga ichki yoki tashqi motivatsiya qanday ta'sir qilishi haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Talabalar ingliz tilini ichki motivatsiyaga ega bo'lganda yaxshiroq o'rganadilar, yoki tashqi motivatsiyaga, ya'ni ba'zi talabalar ingliz tilini tilga qiziqishlari tufayli o'rganadilar. Bu ichki motivatsiya hisoblanib, boshqa talabalar esa ota onasini xohishi, yaxshiroq ishda ishlashni xohlaganligi va shu kabilar tufayli ingliz tilini o'rganishga majbur.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ichki motivatsiya, tashqi motivatsiya, tanqidiy davr gipotezasi, o'smirlar, hukmronlik, muloqot, sotib olish*

Introduction. In current society acquiring foreign languages is taking a predominant role in terms of exchanging ideas and getting in touch with people from all over the world. To identify issues in acquiring a second language and overcome problems scholars are carrying out research. For instance, there has been a plethora of research conducted on the difference between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and their influence on learners' acquiring foreign languages, meanwhile, numerous researches have been done on the critical period hypothesis. Different age level learners, particularly, teenagers can be motivated by a variety of factors such as internal interest, future goals, parents' wishes and to name but a few. Some researchers such as Lightbrown and Spade (2013) noted that "age differences will determine the most appropriate way for teachers to motivate students" (p. 161). Because different age-level learners have various sources of motivation, it is easier for teachers to conduct the lesson. Even though there have been several researches conducted regarding types of motivation and the Critical Period Hypothesis, the dominance of intrinsic or extrinsic motivation in teenagers is faced infrequently. Teenagers are the ones between children

and adults, most of them have already chosen their own way, therefore most teenagers are not taught foreign languages because of their parents’ wish as children, or unlike adults a great number of teenagers don’t work that they don’t have to learn particular FL because of job requirements. Therefore, they have enough time to work on themselves, and to be engaged with their own interests. On the other hand, it is time to think about future perspectives, namely, higher education and finding well-paid jobs. Since I started working, I have faced teenage students who are learning foreign languages because of their own interests, future perspectives, or just their parents’ wishes. So, teenagers are motivated both intrinsically and extrinsically. Therefore, in this research, I intended to investigate which type of motivation is dominant in teenagers taking into consideration their opinions.

Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

Basically, motivation is defined as the driving force behind human behavior. Dörnyei and Ushioda (2001) made an investigation of motivation in teaching and learning and defined this term as “The word motivation derives from the Latin verb *movere* meaning ‘to move’. What moves a person to make certain choices, to engage in action, to expend effort and persist in action – such basic questions lie at the heart of motivation theory and research” (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011, p. 3). There are two types of motivation:

- a) Intrinsic motivation
- b) Extrinsic motivation (instrumental motivation)

People can have an intrinsic motivation to learn a second language when they want to learn internally as Covington and Muller (2001) confirmed, “intrinsic motivation has been defined variously as a tendency to engage in activities for their own sake, just for the pleasure derived in performing them or for the satisfaction of curiosity” (p. 163). Dörnyei (2001) supported that idea concluding that intrinsic motivation connects to mere performance for relishing of taking part in activities. In addition to his statement Stipek (2002) concurs that people are intrinsically motivated to do assignments to improve their abilities.

On the other hand, learners are not always intrinsically motivated to participate in learning foreign languages (Urdan & Turner, 2005). In some situations, there are several external factors that make students be willing to acquire a second language. Vansteenkiste and Lens (2006) define extrinsic motivation as the desire of people to take part in learning in order to gain something different from the task itself such as to get a good job, to pass an examination, and so on. The internal desire isn’t dominant in this type of motivation, but external factors. Brown (2014) supported the idea saying that extrinsic motivation is triggered by parents, peers, and teachers.

Even though there are a plethora of external factors to be impacted, some researchers believe in the dominance of intrinsic motivation in language acquisition. For instance, Maslow (1970) confirms that a learner should have all basic necessities in order to have intrinsic motivation. If basic needs are met, learners can participate actively in acquiring new things. In Maslow’s view of motivation, intrinsic motivation was claimed more powerful than extrinsic in reaching the highest level, self-actualization as the culmination of human achievement in his pyramid (Brown, 2001). It stands for that to learn a new language, students are highly motivated intrinsically.

The importance of Critical Period Hypothesis in language acquisition

In learning a second language, Singleton (1995) states, “younger – better in the long run” (p. 13), however, he points out that there are several exceptions, for instance, most bilingual adults

acquire a second language masterly even though they begin to learn in their adulthood. Several scholars confirm that some aspects of the second language don't depend on the age of learners. There is no critical period in learning vocabulary because vocabulary is learned consciously using declarative memory (Singleton & Lengyel, 1995). According to DeKeyser (2000) "the concept of a critical period for second language acquisition continues to be a controversial topic" (p. 500). Adults can acquire academic English including grammar, complex structures, critical reading, and thinking in the target language, whereas, children are better at pronunciation than native speakers than adults. On the other hand, Johnson and Newport (1989) claim that there is an inference that if the critical period is missed or not exercised it is difficult to acquire foreign languages. From my point of view, the critical period is necessary to learn a second language, however, we can't say after the critical period it is impossible to master a second language. Because we can come across adults learning a second language and using it professionally while communicating with native speakers.

Findings. The research has yielded a number of outstanding features of teenagers. In the first place we have to pay attention to the various languages they are learning. From the research, we can identify that some students who relate not only to other nationalities such as Korean, and Russian, but also some Uzbek students have already acquired English as it is a must for future perspectives. Now they are learning other languages such as Korean and Chinese for their own sake and are willing to listen to music in those languages and watch movies just for entertainment.

The next finding is that among teenagers some of them are motivated by their parents, however, some of them like the language they are learning and can deal with the language well, whereas some of them dislike what they are learning, being stable in the same level even though they have been learning for a year, they don't have any goals of learning the language.

Furthermore, although students are learning foreign languages intrinsically and extrinsically, almost all of them want to speak those languages fluently. From the result, we can confirm that the predominant desire to learn the language is to be able to communicate in that language without difficulties.

In addition, it is comprehended that intrinsic motivation can make learners move on further. When students learn the language they desire internally, they can get better achievements in the learning process even though they have not been learning for a long time.

Conclusion/ Further Implications. To sum everything up, this small-scale research has proved that intrinsic motivation plays a greater role than extrinsic motivation in teenagers acquiring foreign languages. Therefore, this proof can correspond with the statements belong to Maslow (1970) that intrinsic motivation motivates learners to acquire new languages, to develop themselves. It is obviously seen in the survey that students who are internally motivated, are at higher levels rather than those who have external factors. Furthermore, intrinsically motivated students are more likely to be fast in the learning process and they can overcome difficulties easily, they are considered autonomous learners studying at home independently. Almost all internally motivated teenagers are fascinated by communicating in this language with natives, the way of their speaking, pronunciation, music, movies and to name but a few that are an effective way of learning.

There are several points to be taken into account in further research on whether intrinsic motivation will decrease when teenagers become older or stay the same. Furthermore, if the

dominance of intrinsic or extrinsic motivation across age levels is investigated, it would be beneficial research.

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